

The Socio-Economic Conditions of Poor Households: A Forecast Scenario

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Abstract

This study presented the socio-economic conditions of poor households in a city of Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines and provided their possible future conditions using scenario analysis. With posteriori probability estimates revealed that the most probable conditions of poor households would be getting worse as there could be more low earners with low level of education. This condition most likely projected an increase poverty incidence in the City. However, these possible conditions could be moderated through the provision of educational and technical trainings among the young generations thereby equipping them the necessary skills for higher earning jobs strengthened by the opening of job opportunities in the province.

Keywords: Socio-Economic Conditions, Poor, Forecast Scenario, Posteriori Probability, Households, Philippines.

Introduction

An estimate of 11.03% (805 million people) from 7.3 billion people in the world experienced chronic undernourishment in the years 2012-2014. Majority of them lived in developing countries representing 13.5% (791 million) of the population in these countries (FAO, IFAD & WFP, 2014). Poverty incidence is the main cause of this global phenomenon. It is considered as one of the problems face even by developed countries. Identification of different causes of poverty and management practices done by poor in different peculiar environment is a crucial step for poverty reduction strategies.

Poverty reduction commonly refers to lifting as many people from the poverty line through the promotion of economic growth (Barder 2009). Fosu (2011) presented that economic growth for poverty reduction, with emphasis on the role of income inequality is evident in developing countries. With this, there were choices made by the different sectors in the government to reduce poverty like focusing on one dimension such as narrowing income inequality or providing social services for those who cannot afford. On the otherhand, Oxford Poverty and Human Development Initiative (OPHDI) with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) developed the global Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) which emphasized the measurement of factors aside from income-based to determine poverty i.e. health, education and living standards which was then included in the UNDP'd flagship *Human Development Report* in 2010.

On the average, income growth has been the major driving force behind both the declines and increases in poverty. The concept of poverty has evolved from income level or economic capacity to person's vulnerability to social and political forces and his/her deprivation of services such as education and health

care (WDR 2000/2001). Yet, poverty reduction strategies were mainly driven by the government agencies with less participation of the poor. Less consideration was also given in the real scenarios as to the socio-economic conditions of the poor which would form as basis for better managing poverty.

Dapitan City is no exception in terms of the problems on poverty. Regardless of location as to Poblacion, coastal or upland barangays, poor households are prevalent in the City. Since most of the studies done by the government were looking at a macro-level of reducing and solving poverty, the need for micro-level perspective by exploring the socio-economic conditions of the poor is really necessary in order to better understand their situations. The reality as to how they effectively respond to every poverty reduction program depends largely on the appropriateness of such program to their current socio-economic conditions. Looking at the weak points based on their socio-economic status is a better guide in order to attune poverty reduction programs to the more necessary parts that require immediate attention as reflected in their situations. Further, the need to ascertain the socio-economic condition of poor households is of prime consideration as it forecasts the most likely conditions and future of the City.

Methods

The descriptive method of research was used in the study using survey questionnaire in order to gather the data relative to the socio-economic conditions of poor households in Dapitan City, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines. There were 294 respondents distributed to the poor residents in the urban center or Poblacion, mountainous and coastal barangays. The random sampling method was employed in selecting these respondents. Frequency count and percentage were used to determine the proportion of the respondents belonging to a certain category in socio-economic conditions. The data presented were then analyzed utilizing forecast scenario approach.

Results

Socio-Economic Conditions

Family Monthly Income.

Table 1 below shows that almost eighty percent (222 or 75.51%) still earn less than PhP.6,000.00. Only 7.14% of the poor respondents have the income capable of supporting and even staying out of poverty if and only if a family is composed of 5 members with the expected income of at least PHP. 7,017.00 (Virola, 2011).

Table 1 Family Monthly Income

Family Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
PhP. 12,001.00 and above	3	1.02
PhP. 9,001.00 – PhP. 12,000.00	3	1.02
PhP. 6,001.00 – PhP. 9,000.00	15	5.10
PhP. 3,001.00 – PhP. 6,000.00	51	17.35
PhP. 3,000.00 and below	222	75.51
Total	294	100.00

Educational Attainment of Family Members

Education is a factor in setting your position on the wide ranges of job opportunities. In Table 2, the heads of the families in urban areas have a higher level of education since they attended high school education (29 or 28.71%) compared to those heads of the families in mountainous and coastal areas (37 or 37.76% and 24 or 25.26% respectively). The wives in both urban center and coastal areas made more efforts on education than their husbands by finishing high school level (22 or 21.78% and 24 or 25.26% respectively). However,

in mountainous areas, most wives reached the same level of education with their husbands. In general, the urban center has more college graduates than the other areas in the city (8 or 7.92% - husband and 15 or 14.85% - wives). This could be attributed due to the presence of State University and private colleges in the vicinity.

Table 2 Highest Educational Attainment of Family Members

Educ'l Attainment	Urban Center				Mountainous				Coastal Areas			
	Hsb n	%	Wife	%	Hsb n	%	Wife	%	Hsb n	%	Wife	%
College Grad.	8	7.92	15	14.85	2	2.04	1	1.02	1	1.05	5	5.26
Attended College	12	11.88	12	11.88	5	5.10	14	14.29	10	10.53	11	11.58
High School Grad	17	16.83	22	21.78	15	15.31	24	24.49	18	18.95	24	25.26
Attended High School	29	28.71	20	19.80	24	24.49	21	21.43	22	23.16	16	16.84
Elem Grad.	19	18.81	18	17.82	37	37.76	33	33.67	24	25.26	21	22.11
Attended Elem.	6	5.94	8	7.92	5	5.10	2	2.04	13	13.68	14	14.74
Did not attend school	10	9.90	6	5.94	10	10.20	3	3.06	7	7.37	4	4.21
Total	101	100	101	100	98	100.00	98	100.00	95	100.00	95	100.00

Number of Families Supporting Children' Education.

It can be noted in Table 3 that there is a decreasing number of parents supporting their children as they advanced to the higher level of education from elementary up to college level. The bulk of families across all areas or environments are supporting children in elementary level (55 (54.46%), 51 (52.04%), and 59 (62.11%) respectively).

It is quite interesting that families in mountainous has the smallest percentage of parents who reached college level but it is highest as to the number of children supported in college level (15 or 15.31%). The higher the level of education the more expenses it would take to the family.

Table 3 Number of Families Who are Supporting Children's Across Level of Education

Level of Education	Urban Center	Mountainous	Coastal Areas
	Total No. of Families w/ Students	Total No. of Families w/ Students	Total No. of Families w/ Students
College	14(13.86%)	15(15.31%)	12(12.63%)
High School	42(41.58%)	29(29.59%)	33(34.74%)
Elementary	55(54.46%)	51(52.04%)	59(62.11%)
Preschool	25(24.755)	32(32.65%)	17(17.89%)

Heads-of-the-Family by their Primary Occupation.

Table 4 evidently showed that majority of the heads in both in the urban center and coastal areas worked as a carpenter, construction workers or laborers (28 or 27.72% and 29 or 30.53% respectively). It is less expected in coastal areas since only 12 or 12.63% were fisherfolks. On the other hand, those in the mountainous areas as expected worked in the farm (38 or 38.78%). The urban center among other areas in the city provided more job opportunities since it has the lowest percentage of unemployment (5.94%).

Table 4 Distribution of Working Heads-of-the-Family by their Primary Occupation

Occupation	Urban Center		Mountainous Areas		Coastal Areas	
	F	%	F	%	F	%
OFW	1	0.99	0	0.00	0	0.00
Police	1	0.99	0	0.00	0	0.00
Gov't employee (casual)	4	3.96	3	3.06	0	0.00
Security Guard	4	3.96	5	5.10	6	6.32
Contractual Employee	4	3.96	0	0.00	1	1.05
Company/Private Office employee	1	0.99	1	1.02	1	1.05
Carpenter/construction worker/Laborer/janitor	28	27.72	12	12.24	29	30.53
Farmer/coconut farmer	4	3.96	38	38.78	6	6.32
Fisherfolk	11	10.89	7	7.14	12	12.63
Driver – motorcab/bicycle(habal2x), trucks	23	22.77	14	14.29	13	13.68
Waiter	2	1.98	1	1.02	0	0.00
Baker/Cook	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	2.11
Sales Clerk	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	2.11
Electrician/Technician	2	1.98	1	1.02	3	3.16
Derby coordinator/Coordinator	1	0.99	0	0.00	0	0.00
Vendor	8	7.92	4	4.08	2	2.11
Anykind	1	0.99	0	0.00	0	0.00
Unemployed/Non-working/No other work	6	5.94	12	12.24	20	21.05
Total	101	100.00	98	100.00	95	100.00

Technical-Vocational Skills

Technical-vocational skills were really of great help for job opportunities peculiar in one's environment. Depicted in Table 5 that majority of them don't have the technical-vocational skills (71.29%, 55.10%, and 63.16%). In the three areas in the city, most of the family members have acquired cookery which is common among wives. However, commonly acquired technical-vocational skills do not guarantee better job opportunities since they vary from place to place.

Table 5 Number of Families with Technical-Vocational Skills

Technical Skills	Urban Center		Mountainous Areas		Coastal Areas	
	F	%	f	%	f	%
Balot Making	1	0.99	0	0.00	0	0.00
Cosmetology/Beauty Care/Massage	4	3.96	11	11.22	3	3.16
Carpentry	3	2.97	1	1.02	2	2.11
Cookery/Bread and Pastry	13	12.87	27	27.55	24	25.26
Dressmaking	3	2.97	1	1.02	1	1.05
Driving (4-wheel)	2	1.98	1	1.02	2	2.11
Housekeeping	1	0.99	1	1.02	1	1.05
Masonry	1	0.99	0	0.00	1	1.05
Electrical Wiring	1	0.99	0	0.00	0	0.00

Landscaping/Gardening	0	0.00	2	2.04	1	1.05
Painting	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00
Metal works	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00
Automotive/mechanic	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00
No Technical-Vocational Skills	72	71.29	54	55.10	60	63.16
Total	101	100.00	98	100.00	95	100.00

House Ownership

In the Philippine society, the extended family is predominant, particularly in far-flung areas. But Table 6 showed a different perspective among families where more than 75% of the families in the three areas in the city preferred to have a house of their own separate from their parents' house.

Table 6 Family House Ownership

House Ownership	Urban Center	Mountainous	Coastal Areas
Owned by the Family (nuclear)	76(75.25%)	76(77.55%)	72(75.79%)
Owned other than the Family	25(24.75%)	22(22.45%)	23(24.21%)
Common House/ Owned by Parents/relatives	7(0.28%)	17(17.35%)	15(15.79%)
Owned by Sister/ Brother-in-Law	6(0.24%)	3(3.06%)	4(4.21%)
Government owned	2(0.08%)		
Privately owned/for rent	10(0.4%)	2(2.04%)	4(4.21%)
Total	101(100.00%)	98(100.00%)	95 (100.00%)

Assistance from the Local Government

The table below shows the ways the local government helped poor residents. The coastal areas experienced the least assistance from the local government unit (49 or 51.58%). Mountainous areas acquired the highest percentage of help or assistance in terms of 4Ps program, health services and work opportunities and livelihood assistance (17 or 17.35%, 42 or 42.86% and 11 or 11.22% respectively). This is the reason why in mountainous areas, only 23.47% responded that they were not given help or assistance by the local government.

Table 7 Assistance Offered by the Local Government Units

Assistance Offered by the Local Government Units	Urban Center		Mountainous Areas		Coastal Areas	
	f	%	F	%	f	%
Being selected as Pantawid Pampamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) beneficiary	33	32.67%	45	45.92%	34	35.79%
Rendering health services(e.g. free check-up and medicine)	31	30.69%	42	42.86%	14	14.74%
Offering scholarship	1	0.99%	1	1.02%	0	0.00%
Giving Cash Assistance/donation	4	3.96%	1	1.02%	3	3.16%
Offering work opportunities/Livelihood Assistance	7	6.93%	11	11.22%	6	6.32%
Rendering Services through local programs e.g. <i>SerbisyoBilis</i>	1	0.99%	1	1.02%	5	5.26%
Providing water service	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	1	1.05%
Constructing concrete road and other things	1	0.99%	2	2.04%	1	1.05%
Giving food/rice supply	2	1.98%	1	1.02%	0	0.00%
None	38	37.62%	23	23.47%	49	51.58%

Accessibility of Government Service

The table below shows the percentage of poor residents who were able to access government services. It is expected that more programs of the government were implemented in the urban center and accessible to them. As a result, urban center poor residents experienced the highest percentage of accessibility of government services (81.19%) while those in mountainous areas did not consider these services as accessible (61.22%). These programs for the poor were the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps), Supplemental Feed (SF), Livelihood Development Program, Educational Assistance, Financial Assistance and Family Development Sessions.

Table 8 Accessibility of Government Service

Accessibility of government service	Urban Center		Mountainous Areas		Coastal Areas	
	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage	Count	Percentage
Yes	82	81.19%	31	31.63%	68	71.58%
No	11	10.89%	60	61.22%	17	17.89%
Did not respond	8	7.92%	7	7.14%	10	10.53%

Discussion

Socio-Economic Status

Being poor can be attributed to many factors. The opportunity present in the place and the availability of skills among human resources are some of the factors of being poor. Another factor is the programs and projects of political parties responsive to the needs of the constituents for job opportunities. Lack of skills with the presence of work opportunities is useless. The same effect there is in the community with the presence of skills among poor but lack of work opportunities. A worst case scenario is the lack of skills and work opportunities, truly the poor will compete with very limited resources and sometimes leaving no options to survive. This indicates that they were not able to access appropriate livelihood skills training. In a survey conducted among the Social Workers in the City, the need to have marketable skills by attending skills training programs for gainful employment is necessary. About a combined of 92.86% of the poor earned a monthly income below PHP. 7,000.00. This income could not provide enough resources for a family of 5 or more members. Poor families were male-headed since it is the husbands who strive to provide the needs of the family. Although 84.69% are working heads of the family, it did not guarantee the adequate provision of their needs as they belonged to low paying jobs. Wives and children were also working just to augment the limited income of the families but still could not reach the income bracket to support a family of 5 members. The question still lies as to what the local government could do to control the situation.

The urban center still guarantees more work opportunities compared to other areas. It offers more job opportunities in driving, carpentry, construction work and other works that require heavy labor. Only a few are working as office employees. This scenario of poor will continue to exist and the chance of having low earning works prevail since the majority of them did not even finish secondary education. Those few who finished college degrees worked as casual or contractual employees. The worse scenario is that poor families were husband-headed, where husbands have lower education compared to their wives. In this status, limited work opportunities are offered and expected. When compared to mountainous and coastal areas, the majority of working husbands only reached an elementary level of education. As a result, poor in mountainous areas persisted as farmers since they could not engage in more technical works that require a higher level of skills. There were technical skills they acquired but limited only to cooking and pastry. These technical skills did not provide wider opportunities and if there were any could not cater the number of needs. As a whole, the majority of them did not acquire technical skills which could give them avenue on shifting other sources of income.

The lack of proper education is one of the greatest factors of being poor. With limited cognitive resources, poor cannot decide effectively for their situation. For instance, if they were involved in credit institutions they would likely to be so much debt when saving for the future and become independent to start a new source of income is out of their decisions (Mullainathan, S., 2011). They often have limited attention, where they could only focus on their situations looking for food disregarding other things crucial for their improvement. They are experiencing a higher level of stress than those in affluent families, their capacity to think and decide are affected.

It is less expected that poor families in coastal areas resorted to carpentry and hard labor, overpassing the number of those engaged in fishing. This entails that being fisherfolks do not guarantee the providence of the needs of the family due to scanty and unpredictable catch. Poor residents have less capacity to acquire other equipment that would improve their catch. The presence of fishing competitors who have better equipment made their situation even worse. These fisherfolks had no alternative but to shift to other sources of income in the urban center but found few and sometimes nothing.

The type of family and ownership of shelter are significant factors on how poor survive. The more family members live under one roof entails more expenses for those members who earned more and would also lead to dependence from unemployed members. But the sense of cooperation cannot also be taken from this type of family where family members share resources for the survival of the entire family. On the other hand, a nuclear family and owning a house of their own means surviving for their own without greater dependence and support from other relatives. However, expenses can be easily controlled and budgeting would seem to be easy for small members of the family. This is the main reason why families in the different peculiar environment established and owned houses of their own.

Ways of Providing the Needs of the Family in Terms of Education and Health

Poverty is like a cycle, the reason that children's poverty is usually attributed to their parents' poverty as they were exposed to the same environment for years. The economic status of parents affects how they should prepare the future of their children. The provision of education among children would have a higher probability of brighter future than those who were uneducated. Job opportunities and higher salary are attached to those with higher education. This how significant that parents should educate their children.

In the study, all the areas identified have advocated the education of their children by allocating a budget from their income or fund given by the government as 4Ps beneficiaries. From the three areas, it is in the mountainous area showed the highest percentage of parents allocated budget from what they received as 4Ps beneficiaries. On the other hand, there were also recipients of 4Ps program in the urban center but the majority of them did set aside a portion of what they received from the government, rather they saved money from their income to support the education of their children. This is an indication that parents did not properly utilize the fund according to its manifest function. It is also noted that the urban center has the highest percentage of decrease as to the number of parent-beneficiaries of 4Ps program who allocated a portion of the fund for the education of their children. They perceived that basic needs such as food and water were far more important and immediate need than the education of their children.

Assistance from the Local Government

According to Machiavelli (1515), one of the ways to maintain order in a principality is to provide the needs of its people. Providing their needs requires understanding them. The persistence of rulers is most likely guaranteed when the constituents are satisfied. With the long years of similar political leaders holding positions in the city, it is supposedly expected that they have a better understanding of the plight of their people especially the poor and vulnerable portion of the population. However, it did not guarantee a better understanding of their people. As the population in the city grows, there will be worsening of situations as more people need a better understanding from their government. It is noted as well that the portion of poor people who were able to access better government services as to health and education are those in the urban

center and coastal areas. The entire province of Zamboanga del Norte where the city belongs has not guaranteed better job opportunities as more newly graduates migrated to neighboring cities (Campiseño, Baguinat III & Saguin, 2012). This could be attributed to the fact that the Province’s development needs did not match with the program offerings of HEIs in the province thus leaving few opportunities for a skilled portion of the population (Pangilinan & Campiseño, 2012). With this situation, the job opportunities in the province and in the city as well could not support the needs of the entire population.

Scenario Building

The study was interested to forecast the scenarios for the poor households in an urban center, mountainous areas, and coastal areas. The variables considered in this forecast scenario were the social indicator (education) and economic indicator (income).

Figure 1 Forecast Scenarios Based on Income-Education Context of Poor Households

Posteriori Probability Estimates

The probability that the scenarios in Figure 1 will happen are denoted by P(+,+), P(-,+), P(-,-), and P(+,-) respectively. Thus, based on the baseline data:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(+,+) &= P(\text{High Income, High Education}) \\
 &= P(\text{Income is } \geq \text{PhP. 6,000.00, Reached College Level}) \\
 &= \frac{21}{294} \times \frac{38}{294} \\
 &= 0.0714 \times 0.1292 \\
 &= 0.00923 \times 100 \\
 &= 0.923\% \text{ or } \approx 1\%
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(+,-) &= P(\text{High Income, Low Education}) \\
 &= 0.0714 \times \frac{256}{294} \\
 &= 0.0714 \times 0.8707 \\
 &= 0.0622 \times 100 \\
 &= 6.22\%
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(-,-) &= P(\text{Low Income, Low Education}) \\
 &= \frac{273}{294} \times 0.8707 \\
 &= 0.9286 \times 0.8707 \\
 &= 0.8085 \times 100 \\
 &= 80.85\%
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P (-,+) &= P (\text{Low Income, High Education}) \\ &= 1 - 0.01 - 0.0622 - 0.8085 \\ &= 0.1193 \times 100 \\ &= 11.93\% \end{aligned}$$

Based on the above probability estimates two scenarios will be most likely:

Scenario 1: Low Income – Low Education Scenario

This scenario has the highest probability estimates of 80%. This implies that there will be more poor households with low education to remain in their situation or most probably increase its incidence. Poor households in urban areas will remain in their low paying jobs like construction, carpentry, driving – motorcabs/habal2x, farming for those in mountainous areas and carpentry, construction, and fishing for those in coastal areas. There will be a great tendency on the persistence of their conditions since most of them lack the necessary education and skills to shift for a better paying job or alternative sources of livelihood.

The cycle of poverty will be most likely as the younger generations be exposed to the same social environment and few will be able to reach higher education as their families could not fully support it especially when there is no viable intervention be made on the side of the government coupled with poor people's determination to ameliorate their conditions. Not all of them were members of 4P's programs of the government, despite the membership of some, the financial support from the government did not reach to its proper use – education of their children.

Scenario 2: High-low combination scenarios on the conditions in context

There is a combined probability estimate of 18.15% (6.22% + 11.93%) for those poor households with high income-low education and low income-higher education. There will be chances that those with high education but low income seek for better-paying jobs as they are equipped with skills. They will not be contended with their situations and could not carry it to persist. With this educated portion of the poor, they will strive hard to use the skills acquired and pursue a higher quality of life. They will be exposed and motivated to other social realities compared their plight.

On a similar line, there will be a scenario of low education-high income household as they strive hard to get out of their situations for better chances of living. In this case, they will be engaged in alternative livelihood and will not solely rely on their primary source of income.

Conclusion

The scenario of low education and low-income household will continue to persist. The incidence of poverty in the City will not decrease significantly or may even increase in the next decade. The low education and lack of skills among poor households triggered by few job opportunities offered in the City and in the province as a whole drag them to the poverty line. The need for effective implementation of proactive programs relative to the needs of poor such as additional free scholarships for technical education and inviting more investors that will offer job opportunities could help these households.

The migration of skilled graduates from the City can be mitigated with these opportunities. Maximizing the tourism opportunities in the City could offer alternative livelihood among households dependent on meager resources. Offering more accessible social services for the poor could mitigate the negative effects of their situations.

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